

Decoding Orthodontic Retreatments: A Study of Motivations and Outcomes

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Abstract

Orthodontic retreatment is necessitated by a variety of factors that compromise the stability and effectiveness of initial treatment outcomes. Key reasons for retreatment include:

- 1) **Relapse:** Movement of teeth back to their original positions due to factors such as inadequate retention, patient non-compliance, or underlying periodontal issues.
- 2) **Incomplete Correction:** Insufficient correction of malocclusions or alignment issues during initial treatment, often due to mis-diagnosis or treatment limitations.
- 3) **New Dental Issues:** Emergence of new dental problems, such as spacing or crowding due to dental extractions, erupting teeth, or changes in the dental arch.
- 4) **Changes in Patient Needs:** Shifts in patient's functional or aesthetic goals, necessitating adjustments to align with evolving personal preferences or clinical needs.
- 5) **Technical Failures:** Problems related to appliance failures, such as bracket debonding or wire breakage, which can hinder treatment progress. Understanding these factors is crucial for optimizing orthodontic treatment planning and ensuring long-term success.

Introduction

Over the past thirty years, there has been a consistent increase in adult orthodontics. In the United States, the proportion of adult orthodontic cases rose from 15.4% in 1981 to 21.0% by 2017¹. Additionally, a 2018 survey conducted by the British Orthodontic Society indicated that its members were treating 5% more adult patients in private practice compared to 2016². A significant number of these adult patients likely underwent orthodontic treatment during their adolescence and are often categorized as retreatment patients.

Orthodontists involved in retreatments may encounter patients with heightened expectations regarding both the quality and duration of their treatment. To achieve successful outcomes in these cases, orthodontists need a comprehensive understanding of the potential challenges that could lead to treatment failure. Additionally, implementing an objective system to guide the quality of retreatment completion could improve clinical management and enhance the likelihood of successful results³.

In the context of this increased interest in aesthetics, the need for treatment does not

depend solely on clinical symptoms and signs; attention must be paid to the appearance of the teeth. Among the patients seeking orthodontic treatment is a subgroup who have received treatment previously and decide to seek retreatment. In general, such patients are more concerned with personal appearance and have higher socioeconomic status, independent of the objective need for treatment.

The aim and objective of the current study was to explore the experiences, perceptions, and treatment requirements of patients seeking orthodontic retreatment.

Materials and Methods

An online questionnaire survey of adults seeking first-time orthodontic treatment (control) and retreatment (study) was conducted. The responses from the patient questionnaire, along with records from before the initial treatment and pre-retreatment, including photographs, radiographs, and study models, were reviewed. This was done in conjunction with

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identifying the causes of the original orthodontic failure by a senior and experienced orthodontist.

A structured questionnaire encompassing demographic data and closed ended question was administered to assess the reasons behind orthodontic retreatment and patient awareness. Participants aged between 12-45 years, provided information on age, gender, socio-demographics, Retention history, Reasons for initial treatment and retreatment.

Results

A total of 460 patients were invited to take part in the study, with 200 in the retreatment group and 262 in the first-time treatment group. The response rate for the retreatment group was approximately 50% (99 participants), while the first-time treatment group had a response rate of 40% (100 participants). Incomplete responses were not included in the analysis.

The retreatment group consisted of 20 males and 79 females. The control group had 32 males and 68 females. There were significantly more females than males in both groups (Table 1) with a majority age group of 21-25 years.

Characteristics	Initial Treatment	Retreatment
Gender		
Male	32	20
Female	68	79
Age Groups		
18-28	16	27
29-39	29	28
40-50	27	30
>59	28	14

Table 1: Gender and Age Groups

Out of the 99 retreatment patients, 60 reported receiving a retainer, 29 did not receive one, and 10 were uncertain about whether they had received a retainer. Among those who did receive a retainer, 38 reported following the retainer regimen as prescribed, 20 were non-compliant, and 2 were unsure about their compliance (Table 2).

	Yes	No	Not Sure
Retainers Issued	60	29	10
Reported Compliance	38	20	2

Table 2: Retention History

Respondents could provide multiple answers, so the data was reported as frequency counts rather than the number of individual patients. The primary reasons for seeking orthodontic treatment across all groups were aesthetic concerns, such as crowded teeth, smile enhancing, improving facial profile, spacing between teeth and Malocclusion. Individuals seeking retreatment were often motivated by the relapse of their orig-

inal treatment or its failure to achieve desired results. Fewer people were motivated by issues related to jaw positions, the desire to improve chewing ability, airway concerns, or problems with the jaw joints (Table 3).

Reason	Frequency of Response	
	Initial Treatment	Retreatment
Smile Enhancement	43	37
Improvement of facial profile	27	18
Crowded teeth	48	42
Spacing	19	13

Table 3: Motivation factors

Increase in Retreatment Cases: Class 1 and Class 2 Dental malocclusions show a higher number of retreatment cases, with a significant increase, especially among females. **Decrease in Certain Classes:** Class 2 Skeletal and Class 3 Dental show a decrease in retreatment cases, with Class 3 Dental having a notably lower number in retreatment. **Gender Trends:** Females generally constitute a higher proportion in the retreatment phases compared to the initial treatment (Table 4).

Malocclusion	Initial treatment			Retreatment		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Class 1	3	11	14	7	28	35
Class 2 Dental	3	17	20	6	21	27
Class 2 Skeletal	6	10	16	1	8	9
Class 3 Dental	6	11	17	1	3	4
Class 3 Skeletal	8	7	15	4	9	13
Bimaxillary Protrusion	6	12	18	11	0	11

Table 4: Malocclusion

Discussion

One major debate in adult orthodontics revolves around the difficulties related to long-term post-treatment stability. Despite evidence showing that orthodontists can achieve excellent occlusion, relapse remains a significant issue. This study utilized an online survey to systematically assess responses from a large group of individuals: 99 adults seeking retreatment and 100 first-time treatment seekers.

The study also provided insights into the reasons behind the failure of the original treatment⁵. The situation worsens if iatrogenic issues occur and the orthodontist fails to pay attention to proper canine and lateral guidance, as well as correct alignment and intercuspation during the finishing phase of orthodontic treatment⁶.

In this study, retreatment group consisted of 20 males and 79 females. The control group had 32 males and 68 females. There were significantly more females than males in

both groups with a majority age group of 21-25 years. This finding was in contrast with that of Breece and Nieberg⁷, who reported two-thirds of patients were aged 18-27 years from a sample of 180 first-time adult patients. So this is not in accordance with the study.

In 2011, Pabari et al.¹⁰ found from a study of 172 adult patients at teaching hospitals in the United Kingdom that the reasons adults pursue orthodontic treatment are diverse and multifaceted⁸. Our study examined adult motivations for orthodontic treatment from three angles: (1) the source of motivation, (2) the factors driving motivation, and (3) the level of motivation.

The findings indicated that the majority of participants in both the retreatment (71.1%) and control (68.7%) groups were primarily motivated by their own desires rather than being influenced by their spouse or marital status. Our levels of self-motivation were higher than the 27.1% reported by Oliveira et al.⁹. So this is in accordance with this study.

Our work showed that the main motivation factors or reasons for seeking original treatment, retreatment, and first-time seekers to be aesthetic, namely crooked or crowded teeth.

Typically, one would anticipate that patients seek retreatment due to relapse from inadequate retention compliance. Our expert evaluations and questionnaire data corroborate this expectation. The findings revealed that relapse was often due to poor patient adherence to retainer use, and notably, a significant number of patients had not been provided with any type of retainer at all.

Despite individuals' self-reported concerns and complaints about their dental issues, their readiness to undergo orthodontic treatment again can lead to feelings of insecurity and uncertainty. High anxiety levels among those about to start orthodontic treatment may adversely affect their health related quality of life.

Conclusion

The increasing demand for orthodontic treatment is highly significant and intriguing for orthodontists. However, it's crucial to understand patients' needs and ensure our ability to deliver treatments that meet their expectations effectively. Attentively listening to patients and determining the optimal timing for intervention are essential for the success of orthodontic treatment, thereby reducing the likelihood of requiring future interventions.

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